

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANT
Pseudomonas sp.
RESPIRATORY INFECTION IN
AN 11-MONTH-OLD INTACT
MALE PAINT SHETLAND PONY

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June 27, 2024

RESPIRATORY INFECTION

Can affect all ages

Predisposing factors

Inclement weather

Stress during transport

Poor ventilated housing

Stress due to malnutrition

Infectious cause

Bacteria

Mycotic

Virus

Signalment

- Species: Equine
- Breed: Paint Shetland Pony
- Sex: Male
- Age: 11 months
- Body Weight: 42 kg
- Height: 8.5 hands
- Markings: Blaze, star
- BCS: 3/9

Figure 1. Physical appearance of the patient

Case History

Chief complaint: Bilateral, mucopurulent nasal discharge and inappetence for 3 days.

- No vaccinations and deworming given

Case History

Table 1. Vital signs of the patient

Parameter	Patient	Reference value
Heart rate (bpm)	60	40–60
Respiratory rate (breaths per minute)	40	10–14
Body temperature	36.8	37.2–38.1

Other clinical findings observed:

- Inappetence
- Rough coat
- Presence of green, mucoid ocular discharge
- Nostril flaring
- Pale gums
- Shallow breathing
- Thoracic auscultation: crackles
- Normal urine

Figure 2. Image showing bilateral, greenish-brown, mucopurulent discharge

Figure 3. Image showing the left side of the patient

Figure 4. Image showing the right side of the patient

Diagnosis: Complete Blood Count (CBC)

Table 2. Complete Blood Count (CBC) Results

Parameter	Patient	Reference Value
PCV (%)	37	27–43*
Total RBC (X10 ⁶ /μl)	4.57	6.0–10.4*
Hgb (g/dl)	15.5	10.1–16.1*
MCH (pg)	33.9	13.7–18.2*
MCHC (g/dl)	81.5	35.3–39.3*
MCV (fL)	41.6	37–49*

Parameter	Patient	Reference Value
Platelet (X10 ³ /μl)	220	117–256*
Total WBC (X10 ³ /μl)	16.5	5.6–12.1*
Neutrophil (X10 ³ /μl)	12.05	2.9–8.5*
Lymphocyte(X10 ³ /μl)	3.8	1.2–5.1*
Monocyte(X10 ³ /μl)	0.50	0–0.7*
Eosinophil(X10 ³ /μl)	0.2	0–0.8*
Basophil (X10 ³ /μl)	0	0*

*Aiello, S.E. (2016). *The Merck Veterinary Manual* (11th ed.). Merck & Co., Inc: USA.

Diagnosis: Thoracic Ultrasound

Figure 5. Ultrasound image of the left lung showing lung consolidation. Irregular, hyperechoic lung interface (arrows)

Diagnosis: Bacterial Culture

Table 3. Bacterial culture and antibiotic sensitivity testing results

Sample submitted	Species	Sensitive	Resistant
Nasal Swab	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	Erythromycin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Norfloxacin Streptomycin Tetracycline	Ampicillin Trimethoprim

Figure 5. Collection of sample

Figure 6. Growth of *Pseudomonas* sp. in blood agar plate

Differential Diagnosis

Table 4. Differential Diagnosis

Respiratory Diseases	Type of Discharge	Color	Bilateral	Fever	Odor	Lethargy	Ocular Discharge	Nostril Flaring	Neutrophilia	Leukocytosis
Heaves	Serous to mucoserous	White to yellow	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-
Bacterial Pneumonia	Purulent to mucopurulent	Yellow, green, or cream	+	Varied	Varied	+	+	+	+	+
Viral Respiratory Infection	Serous to Mucoserous	Gray or yellow	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
Fungal Pneumonia	Serous to mucopurulent	Yellowish to honey	Varied	+	Varied	+	-	+	+	-
Aspiration Pneumonia	Contain feed material	Reddish brown or green	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+

Definitive Diagnosis

Respiratory Diseases	Type of Discharge	Color	Bilateral	Fever	Odor	Lethargy	Ocular Discharge	Nostril Flaring	Neutrophilia	Leukocytosis
Heaves	Serous to mucoserous	White to yellow	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-
Bacterial Pneumonia	Purulent to mucopurulent	Yellow, green, or cream	+	Varied	Varied	+	+	+	+	+
Viral Respiratory Infection	Serous to Mucoserous	Gray or yellow	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
Fungal Pneumonia	Serous to mucopurulent	Yellowish to honey	Varied	+	Varied	+	-	+	+	-
Aspiration Pneumonia	Contain feed material	Reddish brown or green	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+

Pseudomonas sp.

- Gram-negative rods
- Environmental and opportunistic pathogen
- Opportunistic infection in reproductive tract, lower respiratory tract, eyes, skin, and guttural pouch
- Outer membrane less permeable to antibiotics
- Intrinsic resistance (efflux system)
- Antibiotic inactivating enzyme

Development
of
antimicrobial
resistance

Antimicrobial Resistance

- Difficult to treat diseases
- Costly medications
- Threat to human population

Management and Treatment

MANAGEMENT

- 1.) Daily cleaning of nostrils
- 2.) Addition of beddings
- 3.) Installation of lightbulb

TREATMENT

1. 2.1 ml Gentamicin (Gentamycin 10%®) 100 mg/ml IM BID for 7d
2. 5 ml *Mangifera indica* + *Withania somnifera* + *Embllica officinalis* + *Ocimum sanctum* (Zist®) PO SID for 30d
3. 7 ml Eucalyptus extract + Glycyrrhiza + *Mentha piperita* + Thymus extract + Phosphoric acid (Respower®) PO SID for 30d
4. 2 ml L-Carnitine and D-Panthenol oral paste (Carniko®) PO SID for 30d
5. 5 ml Ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) 250 mg/ml, IM q3d for 30d

Figure 7. Treatment given to the animal

Follow-up and Recovery

09-24-23

- Increased appetite
- RR at 80 brpm
- Decreased nasal Discharge

09-27-23

- Increased appetite
- Decreased nasal discharge

09-28-23

- Increased appetite
- No nasal discharge present

09-30-23

- Active
- No nasal discharge present

10-04-23

- Veterinarian visit

Table 5. Vital signs of the patient after treatment

Parameter	Patient	Reference value
Heart rate (bpm)	60	40-60
Respiratory rate (breaths per minute)	28	10-14

Other clinical findings:

- Alert
- Dry nose
- Clear lung sounds (left and right)
- BCS at 5/9

Figure 8. Physical appearance after treatment

Figure 9. No nasal discharge observed

Recommendations

MANAGEMENT

1. Vaccinations and deworming
2. Supplementation of Vitamin B complex with iron
3. Advise the use of low-dust and mold-free beddings

References

Aiello, S.E. (2016). *The Merck Veterinary Manual* (11th ed.). Merck & Co., Inc: USA.

Couëtil, L., & Hawkings, J. (2013). *Respiratory Diseases of the Horse*. Manson Publishing Ltd: United Kingdom. pp. 78–85, 86–95.

Markey, B., Leonard, F., Archambault, M., Cullinane, A., & Maguire, D. (2013). *Clinical Veterinary Microbiology* (2nd ed.). Elsevier: USA. pp. 275–276.

Pachori, P., Gothwal, R., & Gandhi, P. (2019). Emergence of antibiotic resistance *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in intensive care unit; a critical review. *Genes & diseases*, 6(2), 109–119.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gendis.2019.04.001>

Pottier, M., Castagnet, S., Gravey, F., Leduc, G., Sévin, C., Petry, S., Giard, J. C., Le Hello, S., & Léon, A. (2022). Antimicrobial Resistance and Genetic Diversity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Strains Isolated from Equine and Other Veterinary Samples. *Pathogens (Basel, Switzerland)*, 12(1), 64.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens12010064>

Reed, S.M., Bayly, W.M., & Sellon, D.C. (2010). *Equine Internal Medicine*. Elsevier: USA. pp. 332–336

Rush, B., & Mair, T. (2004). *Equine Respiratory Diseases*. Blackwell Science Ltd: USA. pp. 251–254, 285–289

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